

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 41

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 41

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 41:0 For the choir director. A Psalm of David.</p>	<p>Psa. 41:1 לְמִנְצֵחַ מְזֻמָּר</p>
<p>Psa. 41:1 How blessed is he who ^aconsiders the ¹helpless; The LORD will deliver him ^bin a day of ²trouble. ² The LORD will ^aprotect him and keep him alive, And he shall ¹be called ^bblessed upon the earth; And ^cdo not give him over to the desire of his enemies. ³ The LORD will sustain him upon his sickbed; In his illness, You ¹restore him to health.</p>	<p>לְדָוִד : ² אֲשֶׁר־יִמְלִיכֵהוּ אֱלֹ- הִים בְּיוֹם רָעָה יִמְלִיכֵהוּ יְהוָה : ³ יְהוָה אִישׁ מְרַחֵם וַיְחַיֵּהוּ יֵאֱשָׁר [וְ] [אֲשֶׁר] בְּאֶרֶץ וְאֵל-תְּהַלְלֵהוּ בְּנֶפֶשׁ אֵיבָיו : ⁴ יְהוָה יִסְעָדֶנּוּ עַל- עַרְשׁ דָּוִי כָּל-מְשַׁכְּבוֹ הַפֶּכֶת בְּחַלְיוֹ : ⁵ אֲנִי-אֶמְרָתִי יְהוָה חַנּוּנִי רַפָּאָה נַפְשִׁי כִי-</p>
<p>Psa. 41:4 As for me, I said, "O LORD, be gracious to me; ^aHeal my soul, for ^bI have sinned against You." ⁵ My enemies ^aspeak evil against me,</p>	<p>חַטָּאתִי לָךְ : ⁶ אֵוִיבֵי יֹאמְרוּ רַע לִי מִתִּי יְמוּת וְאָבַד שְׁמוֹ : ⁷ וְאִם-בָּא לְרֹאזוֹת </p>

"When will he die, and his name perish?"

⁶ And ¹when he comes to see *me*, he ^aspeaks ²falsehood;

His heart gathers wickedness to itself;

When he goes outside, he tells it.

⁷ All who hate me whisper together against me;

Against me they ^adevise my hurt, *saying*,

⁸ "A wicked thing is poured out ¹upon him,

That when he lies down, he will ^anot rise up again."

⁹ Even my ^aclose friend in whom I trusted,

Who ate my bread,

Has lifted up his heel against me.

Psa. 41:10 But You, O LORD, be gracious to me and ^araise me up,

That I may repay them.

¹¹ By this I know that ^aYou are pleased with me,

Because ^bmy enemy does not shout in triumph over me.

שׁוּא יִדְבַר לְבוֹ יִקְבֹּץ-אָוֶן

לֹא יֵצֵא לַחַוֵּץ יִדְבַר : ⁸ זַחַד

עָלַי יִתְלַחֲשׁוּ כָל-שִׁנְאֵי עָלַי

וַיִּתְשָׁבוּ רָעָה לִי : ⁹ דְּבַר-

בְּלִיעַל יִצְוֹק בּוֹ וַאֲשֶׁר שָׁכַב

לֹא-יוֹסִיף לָקוּם : ¹⁰ גַּם-אִישׁ

שְׁלוֹמִי וַאֲשֶׁר-בִּטְחֹתַי בּוֹ

אוֹכַל לַחֲמֵי הַגִּדּוּל עָלַי

עָקַב : ¹¹ וְאַתָּה יְהוָה חֲנֻנִי

וְהַקִּימֵנִי וַאֲשַׁלְמָה לָהֶם : ¹²

בְּזֹאת יִדְעֵתִי כִי-חִפְצָתָ בִּי

כִּי לֹא-יִרְיעַ אִיבֵי עָלַי : ¹³

וְאַנִּי בְּתַמִּי תַמְכֹתָ בִּי

וְתִצִּיבֵנִי לְפָנֶיךָ לְעוֹלָם : ¹⁴

¹² As for me, "You uphold me in my integrity,

And You set me ^bin Your presence forever.

Psa. 41:13 "Blessed be the LORD, the God of Israel,

From everlasting to everlasting.

Amen and Amen.

בְּרוּךְ יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵי יִשְׂרָאֵל
מִהָעוֹלָם וְעַד הָעוֹלָם אָמֵן |
וְאָמֵן :

References

<p>Psalm 41:1</p> <p>¹Or <i>poor</i></p> <p>²Or <i>evil</i></p> <p>^aPs 82:3, 4; Prov 14:21</p> <p>^bPs 27:5; 37:19</p> <p>Psalm 41:2</p> <p>¹Or <i>be blessed</i></p> <p>^aPs 37:28</p> <p>^bPs 37:22</p> <p>^cPs 27:12</p> <p>Psalm 41:3</p> <p>¹Lit <i>turn all his bed</i></p> <p>Psalm 41:4</p> <p>^aPs 6:2; 103:3; 147:3</p> <p>^bPs 51:4</p> <p>Psalm 41:5</p> <p>^aPs 38:12</p> <p>Psalm 41:6</p> <p>¹Or <i>if he</i></p> <p>²Or <i>emptiness</i></p>	<p>Psalm 41:10</p> <p>^aPs 3:3</p> <p>Psalm 41:11</p> <p>^aPs 37:23; 147:11</p> <p>^bPs 25:2</p> <p>Psalm 41:12</p> <p>^aPs 18:32; 37:17; 63:8</p> <p>^bJob 36:7; Ps 21:6</p> <p>Psalm 41:13</p> <p>^aPs 72:18, 19; 89:52; 106:48; 150:6</p>
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^aPs 12:2; 62:4; Prov 26:24-26

Psalm 41:7

^aPs 56:5

Psalm 41:8

¹Or *within*

^aPs 71:10, 11

Psalm 41:9

^a2 Sam 15:12; Job 19:13, 19; Ps 55:12, 13, 20; Jer 20:10; Mic 7:5; Matt 26:23; Luke 22:21; John 13:18

Targum

Psa. 41:1 For praise; a psalm of David. ² Happy the man who is wise to show mercy to the humble and poor on the day of evil; the LORD will deliver him. ³ The LORD will keep him and preserve him and do well to him in the land; and he will not hand him over to the will of his enemies. ⁴ The word of the LORD will aid him in his life, and be revealed to him on the bed of his sickness to preserve him; you have reversed wholly his bed in the time of his sickness and rebuke. ⁵ I said: O LORD, have mercy on me; heal my soul, for I have sinned in your presence. ⁶ My enemies will speak evil about me: "When will he die and his name perish?" ⁷ And if he comes to welcome me, he will speak falsehood; in his mind he will gather iniquity to himself, he will go outside [and] speak. ⁸ All my enemies speak together about me in secret, plotting ruin for me. ⁹ He will pour out on him the speech of an oppressor, and will say, "This one who is sick will not get up again." ¹⁰ Even a man who seeks my welfare, in whom I trusted, feeding him my meal – he has cunningly prevailed over me. ¹¹ But you, O LORD, have mercy on me, and raise me up from illness; and I will pay them back. ¹² By this I know that you have favored me, that my enemy has not prevailed over me to cause harm. ¹³ But I, for my blamelessness – you have sustained me; and you made me stand in your presence forever. ¹⁴ Blessed be the name of the LORD God of Israel, from this world to the world to come; the righteous will say, "Amen and amen."

Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual rewrite for the verses is in bold.

Introduction

In David's day, sickness was considered a push from the LORD because He was displeased with something in one's morality. David was upset because he had an illness that prevented him from building the LORD's Temple in Jerusalem. However, the LORD cured him of his illness so that he could gather together the materials and develop the plans for the Temple that his son Solomo was going to complete.

Superscript

לְמִנְצַחַת מְזִמּוֹר לְדָוִד (lam'nctzacha meez'mor l'david) – means "To Him who grants victory, a psalm of David." The spiritual awareness in this superscript is that David called upon the Sefirah Netzach for success over his illness and enemies.

To Netzach, a Psalm of David.

Verse one, two, and three

There is a constant shift between the second and third person, making it difficult to interpret the verses. Spiritual awareness is found in Hirsch's translation.

Progress is with him who gives understanding care to him that has been brought low; the LORD will deliver him on the day of disaster.

The LORD will preserve him and keep him alive, and he will yet be happy on earth; but, even so, you shall not deliver him up to the will of his foes.

The LORD will not let him grow strong upon his bed of illness, but it is you who shall then have transfigured all his lying down during his sickness.

Verses four to nine

David experienced something different during his illness. He prayed for help for the healing of his soul. His enemies rejoiced when they saw his affliction. They wanted him to die. Nevertheless, the LORD did not let David die. He was healed to confront his enemies and be victorious through the Sefirah Netzach.

As for me, I have said, "O LORD grant me Your favor; heal my soul, for I have sinned against You.

My enemies, however, speak evil of me: "When will he die, and his name disappear?"

And if one comes to visit, he speaks only falsehood; his heart gathers that which is used for evil so that once he has gone out, he can speak of it.

They that hate me whisper together against me; they sit beside me and devise evil for me.

An incurable ill has been cast upon him; now that he is laid low he shall rise again no more.

Even the man of my peace in whom I had put my trust, who eats my bread, lifts up his heel against me in contempt.

Verses 10 and 11

But You, O LORD, deal kindly with me and raise me up, and then I shall repay them.

By this I know that You are pleased with me, because my enemy does not shout in triumph over me.

Verse 12

David was aware that the LORD's support would always be with him as long as he devoted himself to the discharge of his tasks and duties

As for me, You uphold me in my integrity, and You set me in Your presence forever.

Verse 13

בָּרַךְ (Baruch) – means "blessed." In this verse, it means "furthered and brought ever closer to full realization."

**Blessed be the LORD, the God of Israel, from everlasting to everlasting.
Amen and Amen.**

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

To Netzach, a Psalm of David.

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The LORD will preserve him and keep him alive and he will yet be happy on earth; but, even so, you shall not deliver him up to the will of his foes.

The LORD will not let him grow strong upon his bed of illness, but it is you who shall then have transfigured all his lying down during his sickness.

As for me, I have said, "O LORD grant me Your favor; heal my soul, for I have sinned against You.

My enemies, however, speak evil of me: "When will he die, and his name disappear?"

And if one comes to visit, he speaks only falsehood; his heart gathers that which is used for evil so that once he has gone out, he can speak of it.

They that hate me whisper together against me; they sit beside me and devise evil for me.

An incurable ill has been cast upon him; now that he is laid low he shall rise again no more.

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But You, O LORD, deal kindly with me and raise me up, and then I shall repay them. By this I know that You are pleased with me, because my enemy does not shout in triumph over me.

As for me, You uphold me in my integrity, and You set me in Your presence forever.

Blessed be the LORD, the God of Israel, from everlasting to everlasting. Amen and Amen.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

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